

Mediation of Job Satisfaction: The Role of Delegative Leadership Style and Work Environment in Improving Employee Performance

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to influence Delegative Leadership Style and Work Environment on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction on Sub-district Employees in Jember Regency. The population in this study were all Sub-district Employees totaling 750 people with the number of samples collected calculated using the Slovin method of 261 employees and selected using simple random sampling. The data collected used primary data with a questionnaire distribution method. Before data analysis was carried out, a prerequisite analysis test was first conducted which included reliability and validity tests. The data analysis method used was SEM. The results of the study showed that: leadership style has an impact on job satisfaction. The work environment has an impact on job satisfaction. Leadership Style has an impact on Performance. Job satisfaction has an impact on employee performance. Job Satisfaction has an impact on Performance. Leadership Style has an impact on Performance through Job Satisfaction. The environment has an impact on Performance through Job Satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: delegative leadership style, work environment, job satisfaction, employee performance.

INTRODUCTION

This Public Service has received special attention from regional leaders, including in Jember. In addition, the performance of sub-district agencies is still not optimal. This is reflected in the results of the 2023 Performance Realization Measurement in Kota District, such as Summersari, Patrang and Kaliwates. Based on the data obtained on employee performance, it is known that the percentage between the achievements of Kaliwates, Summersari and Patrang District employees in Jember Regency, there are still achievements that are not in accordance with the specified targets. Especially in the first point, namely Improving Service Quality, and the second point Increasing Independence and Community Participation. This needs further research so that the performance of sub-district employees in Jember Regency can improve and be in accordance with the provisions set by the government. In line with work performance, there are factors that are suspected of influencing performance in this study, namely Leadership Style, Work Environment, and Employee Job Satisfaction.

The characteristics of a delegative leadership style are that the leader rarely gives direction, decision-making is handed over to subordinates, and members of the organization are expected to be able to solve all their own problems (Hariyansyah, 2022).

In addition to leadership style, the work environment also has a close relationship with performance (Khoiriyah, 2020). The work environment is everything related to employee activities in the office, which includes the physical and non-physical environment (Sedarmayanti, 2018). A good and healthy work environment can provide comfort, satisfaction, motivation, and creativity to employees, so that they can improve their performance and productivity (Qomariah, 2020).

According to (Mangkunegara, 2019), job satisfaction is "a person's feelings towards work" this means that this kind of job satisfaction conception sees job satisfaction as a result of human interaction with their work environment. Basically, a person at work will feel comfortable and have high loyalty to the company if in their work they get job satisfaction according to what they want (Azhad et al., 2015). This can also have an impact on employee performance in an organization.

Various studies have been conducted to determine the effect of Leadership Style and Work Environment on Performance. However, there are inconsistencies in these studies. Such as research conducted by Arnaldi (2024), which states that Leadership Style has a significant effect on Performance with a significance level of 0.00. Meanwhile, research conducted by Hulu (2024) found the opposite fact, which stated that Leadership Style did not have a significant effect

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on Performance, this is indicated by a significance level of 0.236 which is greater than 0.05.

There is also research conducted by Fadila (2023) which states that Work Environment has a significant effect on Job Satisfaction with a significance level of 0.002. This contradicts the results of research conducted by Fitriyah (2020) which found the fact that Work Environment did not have a significant effect on Job Satisfaction with a significance level of 0.111 which is greater than 0.05.

Based on the description that has been presented, the title taken in this study is "The Influence of Delegative Leadership Style and Work Environment on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable on Sub-district Employees throughout Jember Regency".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance

According to (Wibowo, 2016), performance is a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of an activity, program, policy in realizing the targets, objectives, missions, and visions stated in the organization's strategic planning. Meanwhile, Simanjuntak (Hamzah, 2023), states that "performance is the level of achievement of results from the implementation of certain tasks in order to realize the achievement of results to achieve company goals". Performance appraisal is a method used to assess the work performance of an employee whether he has achieved the work targets assigned to him. According to (Dessler, 2020), (2021) performance as the results of the work function/activities of a person or group in an organization that is influenced by various factors to achieve organizational goals within a certain period of time.

Job Satisfaction

The definition that views job satisfaction as a complex emotional reaction. This emotional reaction is the result of the drive, desire, demands and expectations of employees towards work that are connected to the realities felt by employees, thus giving rise to an emotional form that is in the form of feelings of pleasure, satisfaction, or dissatisfaction (Noe, 2015). The definition that states that job satisfaction is an employee's attitude towards work related to work situations, cooperation between employees, rewards received in work, and matters concerning physical and psychological factors (Herman, 2018).

Leadership Style

The leader is interconnected with organizational behavior and effective leadership, which will play a dominant role and contribution in organizational life and always interact with the environment that is always changing continuously both in the internal environment, external environment, and global environment (Rivai & Mulyadi, 2012). Delegative leadership means when a leader

delegates authority to subordinates quite completely (Hasibuan, 2019). Roseni (2020), defines delegative leadership as a leadership style carried out by a leader to his subordinates who have the ability, so that they can carry out their activities that temporarily cannot be carried out by the leader for various reasons. Meanwhile, Pamungkas (2024), Delegative Leadership is where the leader does not need to provide much direction and support. Although problems can always be identified, the responsibility for overcoming and completing tasks can be handed over to subordinates who fall into that category. They are given the trust to carry out plans themselves, determine procedures and technical activities.

Work Environment

The work environment in a company is very important for management to pay attention to. Although the work environment does not carry out the production process in a company, the work environment has a direct influence on the employees who carry out the production process. The work environment is the atmosphere where employees carry out their daily activities (Mangkunegara, 2019).

METHODS

In this study, there are two independent variables, namely Leadership Style symbolized by X1, and Work Environment symbolized by X2. There is one dependent variable, namely Employee Performance symbolized by Y and one intervening variable, namely Job Satisfaction symbolized by Z. In this study, the population to be taken is all sub-district employees in Jember Regency as many as 750 employees. In this study, a sample was used by probability, namely simple random sampling. Of the total 750 employees, the sample used using the Slovin formula was obtained as many as 261 respondents. The data analysis technique used in this study is using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the SmartPLS application. Before conducting the SEM test, an Outer Model Test and an Inner Model Test were conducted, after which a hypothesis test was conducted through direct and indirect influence tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics Results

This study distributed questionnaires to 261 respondents with a sampling technique using the Slovin formula. The answers to the questionnaire will be used to analyze employee characteristics that affect employee performance. This chapter will present a tabulation of respondents based on gender, age, and education, as well as based on respondents' answers to the questionnaire distributed by the researcher. Based on the results of the analysis, it can be seen that the respondents in this study were divided into 159 (61%) male respondents, and 102 (39%) female respondents. Based on the age of the

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respondents in this study, it can be seen that the respondents in this study were respondents aged 21-25 years as many as 33 people (13%), respondents aged 26-30 years as many as 55 people (21%), respondents aged 31-35 years as many as 41 people (16%), respondents aged 36-40 years as many as 48 people (18%), respondents aged 41-45 years as many as 36 people (14%), respondents aged 46-50 years as many as

26 people (10%), and respondents aged 51-55 years as many as 22 people (8%). Based on the education of the respondents, it can be seen that respondents with high school education/equivalent were 129 respondents (49%), respondents with S1 education were 107 respondents (41%), and respondents with S2 education were 25 respondents (10%).

Results of Direct Effect Hypothesis Test

Table 1. Results of Direct Influence Test

Relationship Between Variables	T-Statistics	P- Values	Results
Leadership Style (X1) → Job Satisfaction (Z)	30.371	0.004	Significant
Performance	4.963	0.010	Significant
Job Satisfaction (Z) → Performance (Y)	12.399	0.006	Significant
Work Enviroment (X2) → Job Satisfaction (Z)	4.535	0.008	Significant
Work Enviroment (X2) → Performance (Y)	1.994	0.039	Significant

Based on table 1, it can be seen that all independent variables individually have a significant influence. This is evidenced by the level of significance of variables X1, X2 against Z and variable X1 against Y has a level of significance below 0.05. The Leadership Style variable (X1) on Job Satisfaction (Z) has a T Statistic value of 30,371 with a level of significance of 0.004. The Leadership Style

variable (X1) on Performance (Y) has a T Statistic value of 4,963 with a level of significance of 0.010. While the Work Environment variable (X2) on Job Satisfaction (Z) has a T Statistic value of 4,535 with a level of significance of 0.008. The Work Environment variable (X2) on Performance (Y) has a T Statistic value of 1,994 with a level of significance of 0.039.

Figure 1. Path Analysis

Indirect Effect Test Results

The results of the indirect influence test are presented in Table 2 below. The indirect influence in this

study involves a mediating variable, namely the job satisfaction variable that connects leadership style and work environment with employee performance.

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Table 2. Results of Indirect Effect Test

Relationship Between Variables	T Statistics	P Values	Results
Leadership Style (X1) → Job Satisfaction (Z)→Performance	12.424	0.001	Significant
Work Enviroment (X2) → Job Satisfaction (Z)→ Performance	3.756	0.004	Significant

Based on table 2, it can be seen that all independent variables indirectly have a significant influence through the Intervening variable. This is evidenced by the level of significance of the path $X1 > Z > Y$ which has a significance value of 0.001 with a T statistic of 12,424. While the path $X2 > Z > Y$ also has a level of significance of 0.004 with a T statistic of 3,756. So it can be concluded that indirectly all independent variables (X1 and X2) through the intervening variable (Z) have a significant influence on the dependent variable (Y).

DISCUSION

The Influence of Delegative Leadership Style on Job Satisfaction

After testing and analyzing the data, the results obtained stated that Leadership Style has a significant influence on Job Satisfaction. This is because a good Leadership Style will make subordinates more able to express themselves, so they will feel appreciated by their superiors. In other words, a good delegative leadership style will encourage increased Job Satisfaction. Delegative Leadership Style is characterized by leaders rarely giving direction, decisions are left to subordinates, and it is expected that members of the organization can solve their own problems. Delegative leadership style is very suitable if the staff has high abilities and motivation. Thus, leaders do not give too many instructions to their subordinates, even leaders provide more support to their subordinates. Thus, leadership style can increase job satisfaction (Riyanto et al., 2018), (Anggitaningsih & Handriyono, 2019), (Kosasih, 2018), (Habba et al., 2017).

The Influence of the Work Environment on Job Satisfaction

After testing and analyzing the data, the results obtained stated that the Work Environment has a significant influence on Job Satisfaction. This is because a good Work Environment will increase the spirit of mutual cooperation, increase togetherness, create a sense of helping each other, even beyond what is expected, where this is part of the Work Environment. The work environment is an atmosphere where employees carry out activities every day. With the existence of a work environment, it is expected to increase enthusiasm for work. In other words, a good work environment will encourage increased job satisfaction

(Anggitaningsih & Handriyono, 2019), (Fachreza et al., 2014).

The Influence of Delegative Leadership Style on Performance

After testing and analyzing the data, the results obtained stated that Delegative Leadership Style has a significant influence on Performance. This can also be interpreted that the better the Leadership Style, the better the employee performance. This is because a good delegative leadership style will encourage employees to improve their performance, because the values adopted make employees comfortable at work, have commitment and loyalty and make employees try harder to improve their performance. So it can be concluded that the third hypothesis is accepted. The results of this study support the research conducted by Ismail (2023), (Diah et al., 2024), (Alamanda et al., 2022), (Qomariah, Lusiyati, et al., 2022), (Atikah & Qomariah, 2020), (Sanosra et al., 2022), (Rahman et al., 2024), (Mulyadi et al., 2023), (Wiguna et al., 2022), (Burhanudin & Saputri, 2023), (Triasmawan et al., 2023), (Arifianto et al., 2024), (Qomariah, Estiningsih, et al., 2022), (Yasin et al., 2020), (Anggraini et al., 2024), (Qomariah, Friyanti, et al., 2020), (Qomariah, Rochmadoni, et al., 2023), (Kurniawan et al., 2021), (Qomariah, et al., 2020), (Qomariah, et al., 2023), (Thamrin et al., 2024), (Priyono et al., 2018), (Prasetyo et al., 2024), (Senjaya & Anindita, 2020), (A. Setiawan et al., 2022), (Qomariah, et al., 2020), (Chandra et al., 2020), (Abbas et al., 2020; Arijanto et al., 2022; Ayuningtyas & Utami, 2019; Khan et al., 2021; Listiani et al., 2020; Mohammad et al., 2022; Priyono et al., 2018; Purba et al., 2023), (Bakker et al., 2022; Fikri & Setiawati, 2021; Hadiana & Sari, 2019; Ishak et al., 2019; Kurniawati & Tobing, 2019; Lapatta & Temaluru, 2023; Muizu et al., 2019; Noora et al., 2020; Riyadi, 2020; Udin et al., 2022; Yohana et al., 2020), (Burhanudin & Saputri, 2023), which states that leadership style has a significant influence on performance. Meanwhile, research that is not in line with this research states that leadership style has no impact on performance (Qomariah et al., 2021), (Qomariah, 2012), (Y. Setiawan et al., 2022), (Priyono et al., 2019).

The Influence of the Work Environment on Performance

After testing and analyzing the data, the results obtained stated that the Work Environment has a significant

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influence on Performance. This is because the Work Environment is everything, events, people and others that affect the way people work. A good Work Environment will increase the spirit of mutual cooperation, increase togetherness, create a sense of helping each other, even beyond what is expected, where this is part of the Work Environment. In other words, a good work environment will encourage increased performance (Warsito, 2014), (Munawaroh, 2019), (Widyawati, 2021), (Muhsin & Arifa, 2018), (Wiryawan et al., 2020), (Darmadi, 2020), (Yantika et al., 2018), (Refma & Al, 2021), (Ermawaty & Nugraheni, 2015), (Fachreza et al., 2014), (Saleh et al., 2016), (Fachreza et al., 2014), (Dessy et al., 2018), (Hasibuan & Afrizal, 2019), (Rahim et al., 2017), (Parashakti et al., 2020), (Sare et al., 2023), (Triastuti, 2018), (Prakoso et al., 2014), (Hafifi et al., 2018), (Kurniawati & Tobing, 2019), (Priyono et al., 2018), (Mirawati et al., 2024), (Utomo et al., 2019), (Qomariah, et al., 2020), (Adi et al., 2022),.

The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Performance

After testing and analyzing the data, the results obtained stated that the Job Satisfaction variable had a significant effect on Employee Performance. This is because the higher the level of employee job satisfaction, the more positive feelings about the job will arise which will encourage employees to improve the performance achieved as a form of appreciation for themselves. The term "satisfaction" refers to an individual's general attitude towards their work. A person with a high level of job satisfaction shows a positive attitude towards work. (Handoko, 2015), states that job satisfaction is a pleasant or unpleasant emotional state for employees to view their work. Job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards their work. This is evident in employees' positive attitudes towards work and everything they encounter in their work environment (Alghnimi et al., 2020; Arda, 2017; Changriawan, 2017; Darma & Supriyanto, 2018; Inuwa, 2016; Saleh et al., 2016; Saputra et al., 2016; Shmailan, 2016; Tilaar et al., 2017), (Rostina et al., 2024).

The Influence of Delegative Leadership Style on Performance Through Job Satisfaction

After testing and analyzing the data, the results obtained stated that Leadership Style has a significant influence on Job Satisfaction. This is because a good Leadership Style will make subordinates more able to express themselves, so they will feel appreciated by their superiors. A good delegative leadership style will encourage employees to improve their performance, because the values adopted make employees comfortable at work, have commitment and loyalty and make employees try harder to improve their performance. This incident can trigger employee job satisfaction. In other words, a good delegative

leadership style will encourage increased Job Satisfaction through Job Satisfaction.

The Influence of the Work Environment on Performance Through Job Satisfaction

After testing and analyzing the data, the results obtained stated that the Work Environment through Job Satisfaction has a significant influence on Job Satisfaction. This is because a comfortable Work Environment will increase the spirit of mutual cooperation, increase togetherness, create a sense of helping each other, even beyond what is expected, where this is part of the Work Environment. A comfortable Work Environment can increase job satisfaction. In other words, a good work environment will encourage increased job satisfaction plus employee job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Some conclusions as answers to the main problems raised in this study, include:

- a) Leadership style has an impact on job satisfaction of employees in the District in Jember Regency.
- b) Work Environment has an impact on Job Satisfaction.
- c) Leadership Style applied in the District in Jember Regency has an impact on performance.
- d) The work environment where employees work has an impact on employee performance.
- e) Job satisfaction felt by employees has an impact on Performance.
- f) Delegative leadership style has a positive impact on performance through Job satisfaction.
- g) Work Environment has a positive impact on performance through Job satisfaction.

Based on the results of the study and conclusions, the following suggestions can be made:

- a) For Research Objects, The results of the study indicate that the Work Environment variable on Performance has the lowest level of significance of the other variables. This indicates that the work environment variable still needs special attention in order to improve employee performance.
- b) For further researchers, It is hoped that further research will be expanded by adding other variables related to things that affect the improvement of Employee Performance. such as: organizational behavior variables, individual characteristics, etc.

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